

What Matters When We are in the Middle of Evolving Covid-19 Pandemic?

Ten points to cut through the noise, uncertainty and variety of communications as we are stakeholders and participants in reducing excessive deaths

1. The pandemic consists of a *rolling series of outbreaks* across the world which provides opportunities to anticipate, learn, adapt, and build capabilities for areas later in the series. Learning, adapting and acting effectively leads to reduction in excessive deaths. All have roles to play to accomplish this.

2. *Keeping pace at scale*: its all about matching two rates: challenge and response.

2a. What actions get the rate of infections requiring hospitalization turned around – get transmission rate below 1. The sooner hospitalizations turn around the less hospitals will get overloaded.

Get transmission rate below 1. One way that this happens is when the virus runs out of people to infect (Do Nothing) which provides a baseline. Effective actions break transmission faster, which actions have the biggest impact?

2b. What actions *expand the readiness to respond* to patients needing hospitalization / ICU level care? If you are in the middle of coping with a surge, its difficult to build the capability to care for patients surging in for care.

If the latter capability does not match the growth of patients needing care, the overload increases bad outcomes. What matters is how actions make a difference to reduce excessive deaths, prospectively.

2c. We are in the middle of the challenge – *steering though fog under pressure* when multiple parties are interlinked to get through the field of obstacles.

3. When mismatched, outcomes are worse – *excessive deaths* = ratio of fatalities experienced in a given jurisdiction relative to the best performing jurisdictions. Doing well at matching the two rates reduces excessive deaths. How much? This is hard to know when you are in the middle of the crisis. My estimates are 4x to over 10x. This drive the moral issues (see #9).

4. *Anticipation paradox*: effective counter measures require action in advance of the direct experience of tangible harm, but the ability to engage/mobilize/generate the response mechanisms can be limited without tangible harm (US's inability to get large scale testing). The delays (slow and stale) only serve to make later responses more disruptive and less effective. Anticipation requires ways of acting that build future responsiveness without waiting for definitive information. The current situation highlights that the key issues concern what factors produce saturation of capability at critical points in the response system.

The three fundamental forms of adaptive system break down are visible and operate at multiple levels in parallel: decompensation/anticipation, working at cross purposes/synchronization, stuck in stale approaches/proactive learning

5. Manage the Risk of Saturation/Build Readiness to Respond in Advance of Approaching Overload. When slammed, the key units of action *deploy, mobilize, and generate* response capabilities as the responsible actors on the scene. Other interdependent roles and levels support this by anticipating how medical systems can be overwhelmed and act to generate and mobilize new forms of deployable capabilities. Failure to do so increases excessive deaths ratios.

When challenge events occur at scale, back up resources are also cut or oversubscribed (commonly seen in complex systems and large scale extreme weather events).

6. New forms of *coordination at new scales* are required to respond effectively. Upper echelons of organizations and society become part of real time tempo of operations. If these levels and roles can't synchronize and synergize their response activities, the mismatches grow and excessive death tolls will be higher.

7. The global scale of the Covid-19 challenges have shocked the as-is system. The scale of the challenge reveals how the *obsessive pursuit of optimality* has undermined sources of resilient performance resulting in *severely brittle societies*. Delayed and ineffective responses to Covid-19 in parts of the world reveal the cumulative brittleness that hobble their ability of societies, nations, jurisdictions to rise to meet challenges – where the overall brittleness rolls down to squeeze health care systems as the *crucible* where this challenge must be met regardless.

8. *Solidarity*. Every one is on the scene of the crisis and therefore at risk. Every one is an actor in the evolving outbreaks. Every ones' actions affect the ability to minimize excessive deaths. Promoting social solidarity to pull together is part of responding to the challenge over time event, though the significant time delays in the disease processes make this difficult. Efforts to synergize social solidarity goes well beyond epidemiological simulations that project the scale of infections, overload, and fatalities.

9. *Moral agency* in our crisis is about: can you do some thing to make difference? Where making a difference means reducing excessive deaths and supporting the people near or on the front lines who care for the sickest victims. If you can, then there is *moral imperative to act to make that difference*. Afterwards we will find out more about what actions turned out to be more effective than others, but we are in the crisis and must act on uncertain information. Acting against this principle, puts self above others and puts things above people, plus it means all the measures of effective performance in this crisis are likely to be much worse given what we know in the middle of the response.

10. What allows societies to move or bounce forward as the pandemic resolves? Tom Seager, Dave Alderson and I are proposing four criteria for societies to relax restrictions: do you have the testing infrastructure to test/track/isolate as new cases emerge that could become new hotspots; do you have the ability to ramp up care capacity to provide treatments for all who become seriously ill, while still providing care for non-Covid-19 patient health needs; can you provide safe and effective treatments to promote recovery for patients seriously ill from Covid-19; have you created the ability to build immunity and assess immunity in the population through antibody testing and vaccines. Each of these need to operate at very large scale.